

Results of the analysis of research results on conducting scientific work at the University of Gdańsk

Quantitative data analysis

Gdańsk, 2025

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
BOOST

Study sample

1. Number of surveys:
 - a. sent : 240 (100%)
 - b. completed : 104 (43,33%)
2. Participation rate:
 - a. the survey was completed in its entirety by over 40% of those eligible, which should be considered a result comparable to the results conducted at other universities. Women dominated(73%)
 - b. the study sample consisted of academic researchers employed in three disciplines: linguistics (26%), chemical sciences (39%) and psychology (35%)
 - c. The study sample was diverse in terms of positions held:
 - Assistant – 9%
 - Assistant professor – 55%
 - University professor – 26%
 - Professor – 10%.

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

1a. Are you satisfied with your scientific work – by discipline (scale 1 to 5); differences statistically insignificant

Funded by the European Union

1b. Are you satisfied with your scientific work – by position (scale 1 to 5); statistically significant differences

Funded by the European Union

2. Where do you get support in your scientific work? – (scale 1 to 4);

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

2a. Where do you get support for your scientific work? – from colleagues – by discipline (scale 1 to 4); statistically significant differences

Funded by the European Union

2b. Where do you get support for your scientific work? – from your supervisors – by discipline (scale 1 to 4); differences statistically insignificant

Funded by the European Union

2c. Where do you get support for your scientific work? – from UG organizational units – by discipline (scale 1 to 4); statistically insignificant differences

Funded by the European Union

2d. Where do you get support in your scientific work? – from colleagues – by position (scale 1 to 4); differences statistically insignificant

Funded by the European Union

Uniwersytet Gdański

Związek Uczelni Fahrenheita

2e. Where do you get support for your scientific work? – from your supervisors – by position (scale 1 to 4); differences statistically insignificant

Funded by the European Union

2f. Where do you get support for your scientific work? – from UG organizational units – by position (scale 1 to 4); statistically significant differences

Funded by the European Union

3. Do you feel that you have a person (mentor) you can talk to...? – (scale 1 to 4);

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

3a. Do you feel you have a person (mentor) with whom you can talk about your publishing strategy? – by discipline (scale 1 to 4); statistically significant differences

Funded by the European Union

3b. Do you feel that you have a person (mentor) with whom you can talk about preparing a grant application – by discipline (scale 1 to 4); statistically significant differences

Funded by the European Union

3c. Do you feel that you have a person (mentor) with whom you can talk about implementing your grant application – by discipline (scale 1 to 4); statistically significant differences

Funded by the European Union

3d. Do you feel you have a person (mentor) with whom you can talk about your publishing strategy? – by position (scale 1 to 4); differences statistically insignificant

Funded by the European Union

3e. Do you feel that you have a person (mentor) with whom you can talk about preparing a grant application – by position (scale from 1 to 4); differences statistically insignificant

Funded by the European Union

Uniwersytet Gdański

Związek Uczelni Fahrenheita

3f. Do you feel that you have a person (mentor) with whom you can talk about implementing a grant application – by position (scale from 1 to 4); differences statistically insignificant

Funded by the European Union

Uniwersytet Gdański

Związek Uczelni Fahrenheita

4. Are you satisfied with the current rules for assessing scientific achievements at the University of Gdańsk? (scale 1 to 5)

Funded by the European Union

Uniwersytet Gdański

Związek Uczelni Fahrenheita

CoARA Boost

4a. Are you satisfied with the current rules for assessing scientific achievements at the University of Gdańsk? (scale from 1 to 5) – by discipline; statistically significant differences

Funded by the European Union

4b. Are you satisfied with the current rules for assessing scientific achievements at the University of Gdańsk? (scale from 1 to 5)? – by position; differences statistically insignificant

Funded by the European Union

5. Self-assessment of own activity – (scale from 1 to 6);

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

5a. Self-assessment of one's own publishing activity (scale from 1 to 6); statistically insignificant differences

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

5b. Self-assessment of own grant activity – (scale from 1 to 6) – by discipline; statistically significant differences

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

5c. Self-assessment of one's own activity in the field of scientific development – (scale from 1 to 6) – by discipline; statistically insignificant differences

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

5d. Self-assessment of one's own publishing activity (scale from 1 to 6) – by position (scale from 1 to 6); statistically significant differences

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

5e. Self-assessment of own grant activity – by position – (scale from 1 to 6); statistically insignificant differences

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

5f. Self-assessment of one's own activity in the field of scientific development – (scale from 1 to 6) – by position; statistically significant differences

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost

Links between satisfaction with scientific work and different aspects of research activity

1. There is a positive link between satisfaction with scientific work and:
 - Satisfaction with the principles of scientific evaluation at the University of Gdańsk (correlation 0.40^{**})
 - Received support (correlation 0.32^{**})
 - Having mentors (correlation 0.20^{*})
 - Self-assessment of one's own scientific activity (correlation 0.37^{**}).
2. Linear regression analysis revealed that after taking into account all four predictors, only two of them remain significant. These are:
 - Satisfaction with the principles of scientific assessment at UG (beta was 0.33^{***}), and
 - Self-assessment of one's own scientific activity (beta was 0.30^{**}).

Summary:

1. Over 40% of those eligible took part in the study, which should be assessed as indirect evidence of commitment to work at the university.
2. The results of the conducted studies indicate moderate satisfaction with scientific work (average score – 3.6 on a scale from 1 to 5). This satisfaction clearly increases with the place in the university hierarchy.
3. According to the surveyed employees, they receive the most support in their scientific work from colleagues, slightly less from supervisors, and the least – from the organizational units of the University of Gdańsk.
4. The studies show that in the opinion of the respondents there is a lack of mentors with whom one could talk about the preparation and implementation of grants. Mentoring support in relation to the publication strategy is assessed slightly better.
5. Only less than one in four of the surveyed people expresses satisfaction with the rules in force at the university for assessing scientific achievements, which should be considered a relatively low result.

Summary:

6. The surveyed UG employees evaluate their own scientific activity in different ways. They evaluate their own scientific development and publication activity the highest. They evaluate grant activity the lowest, which is the type of activity in which they lack mentoring support the most.

7. The analysis took into account the role of two important moderators: place in the university hierarchy (position) and affiliation to a specific scientific discipline. Both moderators operate in different ways. In each of the analyses, the statistical significance of the moderators' actions was indicated.

8. The analyses show that the two strongest predictors of satisfaction with scientific work at UG are:

- Satisfaction with the principles of scientific assessment at UG, and
- Self-assessment of one's own scientific activity.

Funded by the
European Union

Uniwersytet
Gdański

Związek
Uczelni
Fahrenheita

CoARA
Boost